

Examining the Impact of Quizlet on Vocabulary Learning in Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language

Yabancılarla Türkçe Öğretiminde Quizlet Uygulamasının Kelime Öğretimine Etkisinin İncelenmesi

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Şükrü BAŞTÜRK

ORCID: 0000-0002-8319-9507 ♦ Bursa Uludağ University, Department of Turkish Language Education,
Associate Professor ♦ basturk@uludag.edu.tr

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kayhan İNAN

ORCID: 0000-0002-7438-0742 ♦ Amasya University, Department of Turkish Language Education,
Associate Professor ♦ kayhan.inan@amasya.edu.tr

Lecturer Aynur AKSEL

ORCID: 0000-0003-0215-476X ♦ Bursa Uludağ University, School of Foreign Languages, Lecturer ♦
aynuraks@uludag.edu.tr

Ph.D. Student Hakan KEKLİK

ORCID: 0000-0003-0912-7588 ♦ Bursa Uludağ University, Department of Turkish Language Education,
Ph.D. Student ♦ hakankeklik@uludag.edu.tr

Ph.D. Student Asuman TUNÇ

ORCID: 0009-0004-2735-4471 ♦ Bursa Uludağ University, Department of Turkish Language Education,
Ph.D. Student ♦ tuncasuman94@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examines the pedagogical role of Quizlet-supported vocabulary instruction in teaching Turkish as a foreign language. Vocabulary knowledge is essential for foreign language proficiency because it supports learners' reading, writing, listening, and speaking skills. In recent years, mobile-assisted language learning tools have increasingly been used to support vocabulary learning through repetition, feedback, interaction, and gamified activities. In this context, Quizlet provides digital flashcards, matching tasks, writing activities, and short tests that may enhance learners' vocabulary practice and engagement. The study was designed as a quasi-experimental pre-test–post-test study with experimental and control groups. The participants were 76 B1-level international learners enrolled in a Turkish as a Foreign Language program at a public university in Türkiye. The experimental group received Quizlet-supported vocabulary instruction for five weeks, while the control group continued textbook-based vocabulary instruction during the same period. Vocabulary knowledge was measured using a researcher-developed achievement test consisting of 50 target words selected from B1-level instructional units. The test was administered before and after the intervention. Since the data did not show normal distribution, nonparametric statistical tests were used. The Mann-Whitney U test indicated no statistically significant difference between the pre-test scores of the experimental and control groups, showing that the groups were comparable before the intervention. Wilcoxon signed-rank test results showed that both groups made statistically significant progress from pre-test to post-test. However, the post-test comparison revealed no statistically significant difference between the two groups. These findings suggest that Quizlet-supported instruction contributed to vocabulary development but did not produce a statistically superior effect compared with textbook-based instruction. Therefore, vocabulary learning appears to be influenced by multiple instructional factors, including structured classroom teaching, repeated exposure, learner engagement, and sustained practice. The study concludes that Quizlet can be used as a supportive and complementary tool in Turkish vocabulary instruction when it is pedagogically integrated into classroom practices.

Keywords: gamification, mobile-assisted language learning, Quizlet, Turkish as a foreign language, vocabulary learning

Turkish Extended Abstract

Teknolojik gelişmeler, yabancı dil öğretiminde kullanılan yöntem ve materyallerin çeşitlenmesini sağlamıştır. Özellikle bilgisayar destekli dil öğreniminden mobil destekli dil öğrenimine doğru yaşanan dönüşüm, öğrenme sürecini sınıf ortamının dışına taşımış ve öğrencilere daha esnek, etkileşimli ve bireysel öğrenme fırsatları sunmuştur. Günümüzde yabancı dil öğrenen öğrenciler, dijital araçları yalnızca iletişim ya da eğlence amacıyla değil aynı zamanda öğrenme süreçlerini desteklemek için de kullanmaktadır. Bu durum, Türkçenin yabancı dil olarak öğretiminde de teknolojik araçların pedagojik açıdan nasıl kullanılabileceği sorusunu önemli hâle getirmiştir. Kelime bilgisi, yabancı dil öğreniminin temel bileşenlerinden biridir. Öğrencilerin okuma, yazma, dinleme ve konuşma becerilerini etkili biçimde geliştirebilmeleri için yeterli düzeyde kelime bilgisine sahip olmaları gerekir. Ancak kelime öğrenimi, yalnızca sınıf içinde yapılan kısa süreli çalışmalarla sınırlı kalmamalı; tekrar, aktif hatırlama, bağlam içinde kullanım ve düzenli maruz kalma yoluyla desteklenmelidir. Bu noktada mobil uygulamalar, öğrencilere kelimeleri farklı biçimlerde tekrar etme, öğrenme sürecini bireyselleştirme ve kendi hızlarında ilerleme imkânı sağlayabilir. Quizlet, kelime öğretiminde yaygın kullanılan dijital araçlardan biridir. Uygulama; dijital kartlar, eşleştirme etkinlikleri, yazma çalışmaları, kısa testler ve oynulaştırılmış tekrar seçenekleriyle öğrencilerin kelime öğrenme sürecini desteklemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Bu özellikleriyle Quizlet, özellikle tekrar ve aktif hatırlama gerektiren kelime öğrenimi için uygun bir yardımcı araç olarak değerlendirilebilir. Bununla birlikte, teknolojik bir aracın öğrenme üzerindeki etkisi yalnızca aracın sahip olduğu özelliklere bağlı değildir. Aracın ders içeriğiyle nasıl bütünleştirildiği, öğretmenin rehberliği, öğrencilerin uygulamayı kullanma biçimi ve öğretim sürecinin genel yapısı da öğrenme sonuçlarını etkileyen önemli faktörlerdir. Bu çalışmanın amacı, yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğretiminde Quizlet destekli kelime öğretiminin pedagojik rolünü incelemektir. Bu doğrultuda, Quizlet destekli öğretim alan deney grubu ile ders kitabı temelli öğretim alan kontrol grubunun kelime öğrenme başarıları karşılaştırılmıştır. Çalışma, yarı deneysel ön test–son test kontrol gruplu desenle yürütülmüştür. Araştırmanın çalışma grubunu, Türkiye'deki bir devlet üniversitesinde Türkçeyi yabancı dil olarak öğrenen B1 düzeyindeki 76 uluslararası öğrenci oluşturmuştur. Katılımcılar, 38 kişilik deney grubu ve 38 kişilik kontrol grubu olmak üzere iki gruba ayrılmıştır. Her iki grup da aynı düzeyde Türkçe öğrenen öğrencilerden oluştuğu için uygulama öncesinde benzer bir

öğretim bağlamına sahiptir. Veri toplama aracı olarak araştırmacılar tarafından geliştirilen bir kelime başarı testi kullanılmıştır. Testte, B1 düzeyindeki öğretim ünitelerinden seçilen 50 hedef kelime yer almıştır. Öğrencilerden verilen kelimeleri tanımlamaları, eş anlamlılarını yazmaları ya da kelimeleri uygun bağlamlarda kullanmaları istenmiştir. Cevaplar doğru ve yanlış olarak puanlanmış, doğru cevaplara 1 puan, yanlış ya da eksik cevaplara 0 puan verilmiştir. Böylece testten alınabilecek en yüksek puan 50 olarak belirlenmiştir. Testin kapsam geçerliği uzman görüşüyle desteklenmiş, güvenirlik katsayısı ise Cronbach Alpha değeriyle .80 olarak hesaplanmıştır. Uygulama süreci beş hafta sürmüştür. İlk hafta her iki gruba ön test uygulanmıştır. Deney grubundaki öğrenciler Quizlet uygulamasına dâhil edilmiş ve araştırmacılar tarafından hazırlanan kelime setleriyle çalışmıştır. Bu süreçte öğrenciler dijital kartlar, eşleştirme, çoktan seçmeli sorular ve yazma etkinlikleri gibi farklı Quizlet etkinliklerini kullanmıştır. Araştırmacılar, uygulama süresince öğrencilere teknik ve pedagojik destek sağlamıştır. Kontrol grubunda ise aynı hedef kelimeler, geleneksel ders kitabı temelli öğretim süreci içinde ele alınmıştır. Beşinci haftanın sonunda her iki gruba son test uygulanmıştır. Verilerin analizinde SPSS programı kullanılmıştır. Verilerin normal dağılım göstermemesi nedeniyle parametrik olmayan testler tercih edilmiştir. Deney ve kontrol gruplarının ön test ve son test puanlarını karşılaştırmak için Mann-Whitney U testi, her grubun kendi içindeki gelişimini belirlemek için ise Wilcoxon işaretli sıralar testi kullanılmıştır. Araştırmanın bulguları, deney ve kontrol gruplarının uygulama öncesindeki kelime bilgisi düzeyleri arasında anlamlı bir fark olmadığını göstermiştir. Mann-Whitney U testi sonucuna göre grupların ön test puanları benzer düzeydedir. Bu durum, uygulama öncesinde iki grubun karşılaştırılabilir olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Deney grubunun ön test ve son test puanları karşılaştırıldığında, öğrencilerin kelime başarılarında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir artış olduğu belirlenmiştir. Bu sonuç, Quizlet destekli kelime öğretiminin öğrencilerin kelime bilgisi gelişimine katkı sağladığını göstermektedir. Quizlet'in tekrar, aktif katılım ve farklı etkinlik türleri sunması, öğrencilerin hedef kelimelerle daha fazla karşılaşmasına ve kelimeleri daha etkili biçimde hatırlamasına yardımcı olmuş olabilir. Kontrol grubunda da ön test ve son test puanları arasında anlamlı bir artış tespit edilmiştir. Bu bulgu, ders kitabı temelli geleneksel öğretim sürecinin de öğrencilerin kelime öğrenimini desteklediğini göstermektedir. Dolayısıyla kelime gelişimi yalnızca dijital bir aracın kullanımına bağlı değildir; yapılandırılmış sınıf içi öğretim, düzenli tekrar ve öğretmen rehberliği de bu süreçte etkili olabilir. Deney ve kontrol gruplarının son test puanları karşılaştırıldığında ise iki grup arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir fark bulunmamıştır. Başka bir ifadeyle, Quizlet kullanan deney grubu gelişim göstermiş olsa da bu gelişim kontrol grubuna göre anlamlı bir üstünlük oluşturmamıştır. Araştırma sonuçları, Quizlet'in yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğretiminde kelime öğrenimini destekleyebilecek tamamlayıcı bir araç olduğunu göstermektedir. Ancak bulgular, Quizlet kullanımının tek başına geleneksel öğretime göre daha üstün bir sonuç üretmediğini ortaya koymuştur. Bu durum, teknoloji destekli dil öğretiminde asıl belirleyici unsurun aracın kendisinden çok, aracın öğretim sürecine nasıl entegre edildiği olduğunu göstermektedir. Quizlet; tekrar, aktif hatırlama, bireysel çalışma ve oyunlaştırılmış etkinlikler yoluyla öğrencilerin kelime öğrenme sürecini destekleyebilir. Bununla birlikte, bu tür uygulamaların etkili olabilmesi için öğretim hedefleriyle uyumlu biçimde planlanması gerekir. Öğretmen rehberliği, düzenli takip, sınıf içi etkinliklerle bütünleştirme ve öğrencilerin uygulamayı bilinçli kullanması, teknolojik araçlardan elde edilecek verimi artırabilir. Sonuç olarak bu çalışma, Quizlet'in yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğretiminde tek başına yeterli bir çözüm değil yapılandırılmış öğretim sürecini destekleyen yardımcı bir araç olarak kullanılabileceğini göstermektedir. Gelecekte yapılacak çalışmaların farklı dil düzeylerinde, daha uzun süreli uygulamalarla ve karma yöntem desenleriyle yürütülmesi, Quizlet ve benzeri dijital araçların kelime öğrenimi üzerindeki etkisini daha ayrıntılı biçimde ortaya koyabilir.

Anahtar Sözcükler: oyunlaştırma, mobil destekli dil öğrenimi, Quizlet, yabancı dil olarak Türkçe, kelime öğrenimi

Introduction

The increasing prevalence of teaching Turkish as a foreign language has highlighted the need to integrate technological components of modern language education more systematically into Turkish language instruction. Alongside the growing use of the internet, rapid developments in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have introduced new possibilities for foreign language learning. Considering the role of technology in education today, the depth of this interaction offers different opportunities for education (Ay & Tapan-BROUTIN, 2024). For learners often described as “born into technology” (Cilliers, 2017), digital tools may enhance engagement; however, their pedagogical value

depends largely on how they are integrated into instructional practices. The emergence of computer-assisted language learning, followed by mobile-assisted language learning, has expanded learning beyond traditional classroom boundaries, offering opportunities for flexible, interactive, and continuous learning. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of such technologies in supporting specific instructional outcomes, such as vocabulary learning, remains closely tied to pedagogical design rather than technological availability alone.

Computer-assisted language learning has gradually evolved into mobile-assisted language learning, expanding the pedagogical possibilities of language education. Mobile technologies have extended learning beyond fixed classroom settings by enabling portability, real-time access, and collaborative engagement (Kukulka-Hulme, 2009). As an extension of CALL, mobile-assisted language learning has been shaped by Web 2.0 environments, allowing learners to engage with language through interactive and repetitive tasks. Features such as digital flashcards, matching activities, and short assessment tasks facilitate distributed and goal-oriented practice over time, which is particularly relevant for vocabulary learning. Moreover, mobile applications can support learner autonomy by providing immediate feedback, audio pronunciation, and gamified elements that enhance engagement when aligned with instructional objectives (Dizon, 2016; Sanosi, 2018). These features are particularly relevant for instructional areas such as vocabulary learning, which benefit from distributed and repeated practice.

In mobile-assisted language learning, instructional processes are often supported through gamified elements designed to enhance learner engagement rather than merely enjoyment (Deterding et al., 2011; Hamari et al., 2014). Beyond general language skill development, mobile applications have been increasingly employed to support vocabulary learning, which plays a central role in both comprehension and production. Consequently, researchers in educational technology have focused on designing and examining digital tools that facilitate vocabulary practice through repetition, feedback, and learner interaction (Kohnke, 2020). Previous studies suggest that such applications may help support vocabulary learning processes, which is widely recognized as one of the more challenging aspects of foreign language learning (Çelik & Toptaş, 2010).

Developing learners' vocabulary knowledge with the support of technological tools has long been emphasized in language education. Vocabulary knowledge is widely recognized as essential for the development of the four language skills and overall proficiency in a second language (Groot, 2000). Without an adequate lexical repertoire, learners may experience difficulties in engaging with grammar, reading, and writing tasks. For this reason, vocabulary learning often extends beyond classroom instruction and requires sustained practice over time. Research suggests that learners benefit from developing individual vocabulary learning strategies while being supported by structured learning environments (Siriwan, 2007). In this context, mobile applications can function as supportive and guiding tools that facilitate vocabulary learning processes. Learning vocabulary through digital applications involves multiple dimensions, including pronunciation, meaning, and morphological and syntactic features (Kalyuga et al., 2013). By offering multimodal resources such as audio input, visual support, and opportunities for repeated exposure, mobile applications may create interactive learning contexts that support vocabulary development (Bueno-Alastuey & Nemeth, 2022). Such characteristics make mobile applications particularly suitable for structured vocabulary instruction in formal language learning contexts.

The teaching of Turkish as a foreign and second language has increasingly engaged with recent developments in educational technology. Previous research highlights that online platforms and mobile applications can support language learning by fostering learner engagement and providing interactive learning opportunities when pedagogically integrated into instruction (İnal & Arslanbaş, 2021; Eryılmaz, 2025; Sarigül, 2021; Yurtseven Yılmaz, 2023). Similarly, Büyükaslan (2007) emphasizes the growing need for educators who can incorporate information technologies into foreign language teaching practices. Within this context, vocabulary-focused mobile applications that combine repetition, learner autonomy, and interactive tasks have attracted particular attention. One such tool is Quizlet, which aligns closely with principles of repetition, learner autonomy, and interactive practice discussed in previous research.

Quizlet is a digital application designed to support vocabulary learning by allowing learners to create personalized word sets and engage with them through various interactive activities. Originally developed in 2005, the platform has been widely adopted in language learning contexts (Quizlet, n.d.). Its instructional design draws on principles such as repetition and active engagement, enabling learners to practice vocabulary through multiple modes, including reading, writing, matching, and testing. These features are intended to facilitate repeated exposure to lexical items and encourage active retrieval, which are considered important for vocabulary development. By offering flexible and learner-controlled practice opportunities, Quizlet provides a structured environment that may support vocabulary learning processes and learner engagement when integrated into instructional contexts.

Although studies have examined the use of digital flashcard applications such as Quizlet in various foreign language contexts (Alizadeh, 2019; Andarab, 2019; Bokor & Kálmán, 2020; Dahl, 2021; García-Ruiz & Gómez-Domínguez, 2019; Montaner-Villalba, 2019; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2021; Pham, 2022), empirical research focusing specifically on the teaching of Turkish as a foreign language remains relatively limited. Moreover, the effectiveness of technology-supported vocabulary learning may vary depending on instructional context, proficiency level, and pedagogical integration. Examining the role of Quizlet within the context of teaching Turkish as a foreign language can provide insights into how technology-supported vocabulary instruction functions in this instructional setting.

Purpose

This study aims to investigate the pedagogical role of Quizlet-supported vocabulary instruction in teaching Turkish as a foreign language. Accordingly, the following research questions guide the study:

1. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test scores of the experimental and control groups?
2. Is there a significant difference between the post-test scores of the experimental and control groups?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental group receiving Quizlet-supported instruction?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the control group receiving textbook-based instruction?

Method

Research Design

The study was designed using a quasi-experimental design, a quantitative research method. A pre-test–post-test design with experimental and control groups was employed to explore differences in vocabulary learning outcomes. Quasi-experimental designs are commonly used in educational research, particularly in classroom-based studies where random assignment of individual learners is not feasible due to institutional and ethical constraints (Balci, 2001; Büyüköztürk, 2007). Accordingly, intact classes with comparable characteristics were assigned to either the experimental or control condition.

Study Group

The study group consisted of 76 international learners of Turkish at the B1 proficiency level who were enrolled in a Turkish as a Foreign Language program at a large public university in Türkiye during the third instructional period of 2024. Two intact classes were assigned to the experimental and control groups, each comprising 38 participants. All learners had successfully completed the A2 level and had recently begun B1-level instruction. The demographic information of the study group participants is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Participant characteristics

Gender	N	%
Female	43	57
Male	33	43
Age	N	%
17-18	29	38
19-20	18	24
21-22	9	12
23-24	7	9
25+	13	17
Education	N	%
High School	52	68
University	18	24
Postgraduate	6	8
Length of stay in Türkiye	N	%
Less than 6 months	66	86
6-12 months	5	7
More than a year	5	7
Total	76	100

Table 1 provides an overview of the participants' demographic characteristics. The study group included learners with diverse backgrounds in terms of age, gender, educational level, and length of stay in Türkiye. Overall, the participants represented a relatively homogeneous instructional context with respect to proficiency level and curricular exposure, which was the primary criterion for inclusion in the study.

When Table 2 is examined, it shows the computer, phone, and internet applications are widely preferred by participants while learning Turkish.

Table 2. Applications used in language learning

Applications used in language learning	N	%
You Tube	65	24.9
Internet	57	21.8
Instagram	40	15.3
Google Translate	31	11.9

Games	21	8.0
Duolingo	19	7.3
TDK Turkish Dictionary	9	3.4
Mondly	4	1.5
Reverso	3	1.1
ChatGPT	2	0.8
Tureng	2	0.8
DeepL	2	0.8
Yandex Translate	2	0.8
Busuu	1	0.4
Udemy	1	0.4
Duocards	1	0.4
IOS Translate	1	0.4
Total	261	100

Participants were allowed to report more than one application; therefore, the total frequency exceeds the number of participants. As shown in Table 2, the majority of participants reported regular use of various digital platforms for language learning purposes, indicating that learners in both groups were familiar with technology-mediated learning environments prior to the instructional intervention and reducing the likelihood that observed outcomes could be attributed solely to novelty effects.

Data Collection Process

Data were collected using a background information form and a researcher-developed vocabulary achievement test administered as pre- and post-tests. The background form was used to gather descriptive information about participants' demographic characteristics and prior exposure to digital tools and was not included as a variable in the statistical analyses.

The vocabulary achievement test consisted of 50 lexical items selected from the B1 units of the Uludağ Turkish Teaching Set, all of which were targeted during the instructional intervention. Care was taken to ensure that the selected items had not been previously introduced to the learners. The test was designed to measure learners' receptive and productive knowledge of the target vocabulary.

Participants were asked to demonstrate their knowledge of each word by providing a definition, a synonym, or an appropriate contextual example. For instance, learners were asked to explain the meaning of a given target word or to use it in a meaningful sentence in Turkish. Responses were scored dichotomously as correct or incorrect based on predefined criteria agreed upon by two experts. Blank, irrelevant, or illegible responses were scored as incorrect. Correct responses were assigned 1 point, while incorrect or incomplete responses were assigned 0 points, resulting in a maximum possible score of 50.

To ensure content validity, the test items were reviewed by a specialist in Turkish language education to confirm their relevance to the instructional objectives and the target vocabulary taught during the intervention. A pilot study was then conducted with 20 learners who were not included in the main study group. Following the pilot implementation, the vocabulary achievement test was reviewed in terms of item clarity, appropriateness for the B1 proficiency level, and consistency with the instructional objectives. Items that were found to be unclear or potentially ambiguous were revised based on expert feedback and learner responses obtained during the pilot study. In addition, items that did not adequately reflect the target vocabulary or caused comprehension difficulties were removed or revised before the final form of the test was prepared. After these revisions, the final

version of the vocabulary achievement test consisted of 50 lexical items. The internal consistency reliability of the final form was calculated using Cronbach's alpha, and the reliability coefficient was found to be .80, indicating acceptable reliability (Büyükoztürk, 2010).

Data Collection Tools

Data were collected over a five-week instructional period. During the first week, the background information form was administered, followed by the pre-test in both the experimental and control groups. In the experimental group, learners were introduced to the Quizlet application and enrolled in a virtual class created for the study. Under the guidance of the researchers, participants completed sample activities to familiarize themselves with the platform.

Throughout the five-week period, Quizlet-based vocabulary activities prepared by the researchers were shared weekly with the experimental group. Each instructional unit included sets of approximately 25 target words comprising verbs, nouns, and adjectives, accompanied by visuals suggested by the application. Learners engaged in activities such as matching, multiple-choice, and writing tasks. The researchers monitored the process by providing instructional guidance and technical support and by ensuring consistent implementation of the activities.

In the control group, vocabulary instruction was conducted using traditional textbook-based methods, relying on the same instructional units and equivalent instructional time as the experimental group. At the end of the fifth week, the post-test was administered to both groups to examine differences in vocabulary learning outcomes.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS. Before conducting the main analyses, the normality of the pre-test and post-test scores was examined using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk normality tests. The results indicated that the scores did not meet the assumption of normal distribution. Therefore, nonparametric statistical procedures were employed in the study.

To assess baseline equivalence between the experimental and control groups, the pre-test scores were compared using the Mann-Whitney U test. To examine within-group changes in vocabulary knowledge over the instructional period, the pre-test and post-test scores of each group were analyzed separately using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Finally, the post-test scores of the experimental and control groups were compared using the Mann-Whitney U test to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference in vocabulary learning outcomes after the intervention.

Ethical Principles

Ethics approval for this study was obtained from the Bursa Uludağ University Research and Publication Ethics Committee (Social and Human Sciences Research and Publication Ethics Committee). The ethics approval was granted on December 18, 2023, with the document number 2023-12. The research was conducted in accordance with ethical standards for studies involving human participants. Prior to participation, all participants were informed about the purpose and procedures of the study, and informed consent was obtained voluntarily from all participants. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and participants were assured that their responses would be used solely for research purposes and kept confidential.

Findings

Preliminary analyses of the pre-test and post-test scores indicated deviations from normality across groups. These results are reported for transparency and to provide context for the statistical procedures employed in the subsequent analyses.

Table 3. Preliminary distributional characteristics of pre- and post-test scores

Pre-test	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	df	Sig.	Statistics	df	Sig.
Exper. Group	.169	38	.008**	.896	38	.002**
Control Group	.162	38	.013*	.921	38	.011*

Post test	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	df	Sig.	Statistics	df	Sig.
Exper. Group	.109	38	.200	.896	38	.011*
Control Group	.120	38	.185	.921	38	.075

*p<.05

The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests indicated that the normality assumption was not consistently met across all pre-test and post-test scores. As shown in Table 3, some distributions did not significantly deviate from normality, whereas others showed statistically significant deviations from normal distribution. In particular, the pre-test scores and some post-test scores yielded significance values below .05. Therefore, considering the overall distributional pattern of the data and the quasi-experimental design of the study, nonparametric statistical procedures were preferred for the subsequent analyses.

Findings Regarding Pre-Test Results of the Experimental and Control Groups

The first research question investigated whether there was a significant difference between the pre-test scores of the control and experimental groups. In this context, the Mann-Whitney U Test results were examined.

Table 4. Mann-Whitney U Test Results Comparing the Pre-Test Results of the Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	\bar{X}	Rank Average	Rank Total	U	p
Exper. Group	38	12.18	35.57	1351.0		
Control Group	38	15.79	41.43	1574.50	610.50	.248

p>.05

Table 4 shows that the mean rank of the experimental group participants (35.57) was lower than that of the control group (41.43). This means that the control group's pre-test scores were slightly higher overall. However, the Mann-Whitney U test results (U=610.50, p=.248) reveal no statistically significant difference between the groups (p>.05). According to this result, the pre-test scores of the experimental and control groups were similar. No significant difference in achievement was determined between the groups.

Findings Regarding the Post-Test Results of the Experimental Group and the Control Group

The second research question investigated whether there was a significant difference between the post-test scores of the control and experimental groups. In this context, the results of the Mann-Whitney U Test were examined.

Table 5. Mann-Whitney U Test Results Comparing the Post-Test Results of the Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	\bar{X}	Rank Average	Rank Total	U	p
Exper. Group	38	25.42	39.66	1507.00		
Control Group	38	24.58	37.34	1419.00	766.00	.651

$p > .05$

Table 5, which compares the posttest results of the experimental and control groups, shows that the mean post-test score of the experimental group participants was 25.42, while the mean post-test score of the control group participants was 24.58. The mean rank of the experimental group was 39.66, and the control group was 37.34. The Mann-Whitney U test result ($U=766.00$, $p=.651$) indicates that the difference between the two groups was not statistically significant ($p > .05$). This result suggests that the post-test success levels of the experimental and control groups were quite similar, and that even if the treatment was considered to have contributed to the experimental group, this contribution did not create a statistically significant superiority over the control group.

Findings Regarding the Difference Between Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Experimental Group

The third question of the study sought to answer whether there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results of the experimental group participants who were taught vocabulary through the Quizlet application.

Table 6. Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Results Comparing Pre-Test-Post-Test Scores of the Experimental Group

Experimental Group	N	Rank Average	Rank Total	Z	p
Negative Rank	1	4.50	4.50		
Positive Rank	37	19.91	736.50	-5.636	.001
Equal	0				

$p = .001$

According to Table 6, there is a statistically significant difference between the achievement scores of the experimental group participants before and after the intervention ($Z=-5.636$, $p < .001$). The negative rank sum of the academic achievement test for the experimental group participants was calculated as 4.50, and the positive rank sum was calculated as 736.50. An examination of the mean rank and total difference scores reveals that the difference favors the positive ranks. The participants' post-test scores were significantly higher than their pretest scores. This result indicates that almost all participants in the experimental group improved their test scores at the end of the intervention period.

Findings Regarding the Difference Between Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Control Group

The fourth question of the study examined whether there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the control group participants who did not use the Quizlet application.

Table 7. Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Results Comparing Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Control Group

Control Group	N	Rank Average	Rank Total	Z	p
---------------	---	--------------	------------	---	---

Negative Rank	2	17.50	35.00		
Positive Rank	36	19.61	706.00	-3.059	.001
Equal	0				

$p=.001$

Table 7 shows a statistically significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the control group participants ($Z=-3.059$, $p<.001$). The negative rank sum of the academic achievement test scores of the control group participants was calculated as 35.00, and the positive rank sum was calculated as 706.00. When the mean ranks and total difference scores are examined, it can be said that the difference is in favor of the positive ranks. According to these results, the post-test scores of the control group participants are significantly higher than their pre-test scores.

Discussion

This study examined the pedagogical role of Quizlet-supported vocabulary instruction in teaching Turkish as a foreign language. The findings indicate that learners in the experimental group demonstrated a significant increase in vocabulary knowledge over the instructional period. A similar improvement was also observed in the control group, and no statistically significant difference was found between the post-test performances of the two groups. Rather than indicating the ineffectiveness of the application, these results suggest that vocabulary development was shaped by multiple instructional factors, including structured classroom instruction, sustained exposure, and opportunities for practice.

The significant within-group improvement observed in the experimental group suggests that Quizlet functioned as a supportive tool for vocabulary practice, particularly by providing repeated exposure and opportunities for active engagement. These findings align with previous research highlighting the potential of digital flashcard applications to support vocabulary learning through repetition and retrieval practice (Dizon, 2016; Sanosi, 2018; Waluyo & Bucol, 2021). However, the absence of a significant difference between the experimental and control groups indicates that the use of Quizlet alone was not sufficient to produce superior learning outcomes beyond those achieved through traditional instructional methods.

This pattern of results is consistent with studies suggesting that the pedagogical impact of Quizlet may vary depending on instructional context, learner characteristics, and the ways in which the application is integrated into classroom practice (Okkan & Aydın, 2020). Platzer (2020) noted that certain modes within the application, such as matching activities, may contribute less to durable vocabulary learning when used in isolation. From this perspective, the present findings suggest that the effectiveness of Quizlet should be understood not as an inherent property of the tool itself, but as contingent upon pedagogical design and instructional alignment.

In the context of teaching Turkish as a foreign language, the findings partially diverge from studies reporting strong positive effects of Quizlet on vocabulary acquisition (e.g., Eyibil & Göçen, 2025). This divergence may be attributed to differences in proficiency level, instructional duration, or patterns of application use. Taken together, the results of the present study contribute to the growing body of CALL research by highlighting the importance of contextual and pedagogical factors in technology-enhanced vocabulary instruction.

Overall, the findings suggest that Quizlet can support vocabulary development as a complementary instructional tool, rather than as a standalone solution. When integrated into

structured instructional contexts and combined with guided classroom activities, the application may facilitate learner engagement and individual progress over time.

Conclusion

This study investigated the pedagogical role of Quizlet-supported vocabulary instruction in teaching Turkish as a foreign language. The findings indicate that while learners in the experimental group demonstrated significant improvement in vocabulary knowledge over the instructional period, similar gains were also observed in the control group, and no statistically significant difference emerged between the post-test performances of the two groups. These results suggest that vocabulary development is influenced by multiple instructional factors rather than by the use of a single technological tool alone.

From a pedagogical perspective, the findings highlight that Quizlet can function as a supportive and complementary tool within structured instructional contexts. When integrated alongside guided classroom instruction and sustained practice, digital applications may contribute to learner engagement and individual progress. However, the results also underscore the importance of pedagogical design in technology-enhanced language learning, suggesting that instructional alignment and context play a central role in shaping learning outcomes.

Implications for Practice and Research

Despite these limitations, the findings of the present study offer several implications for language teaching practice and future research. From a pedagogical perspective, the results suggest that Quizlet can serve as a supportive tool for vocabulary learning when integrated into structured instructional contexts. Rather than functioning as a standalone solution, digital vocabulary applications appear to be most effective when aligned with guided classroom instruction, curricular goals, and opportunities for repeated practice.

For instructional design, the findings highlight the importance of pedagogical alignment over technological novelty. The absence of a significant difference between groups suggests that technology-enhanced learning outcomes are shaped less by the tool itself and more by how it is embedded within instructional practices. Teachers are therefore encouraged to consider how digital tools are used, which application modes are emphasized, and how learners are guided in their engagement with technology-based activities.

In terms of future research, further studies may explore the effects of technology-supported vocabulary learning across different proficiency levels, instructional durations, and learning contexts. Longitudinal designs could provide insights into retention and transfer effects, while mixed-method approaches may help uncover learners' experiences, engagement patterns, and strategy use. Additionally, comparative studies examining different digital tools or combinations of tools may contribute to a more nuanced understanding of technology integration in vocabulary instruction.

References

- Alizadeh, M. (2019). Quizlet as a tool for enhancing autonomous learning of English vocabulary. *Teaching English with Technology*, 19(3), 34-52. <https://www.tewtjournal.org>
- Andarab, M. S. (2019). Learning vocabulary through collocating on Quizlet. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 7(4), 980-985. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2019.070409>

- Ay, S., & Tapan-Broutin, M. S. (2024). A comparative examination of fifth-grade middle school students' and the ChatGPT artificial intelligence tool's experiences with pattern tasks [Ortaokul beşinci sınıf öğrencileri ile ChatGPT yapay zekâ aracının örüntü görevleri deneyimlerinin karşılaştırmalı incelenmesi]. *Uluslararası İnsan ve Sanat Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 9(4), 294–320. <https://izlik.org/JA99DC55PY>
- Balcı, A. (2001). *Sosyal bilimlerde araştırma: Yöntem, teknik ve ilkeler*. Pegem A Yayıncılık.
- Bokor, A., & Kálmán, C. (2020). The efficiency of Quizlet-based EFL vocabulary learning in preparing undergraduates for state English exam. *Romanian Journal of English Studies*, 17(1), 14-23. <https://doi.org/10.1515/rjes-2020-0003>
- Bueno-Alastuey, M. C., & Nemeth, K. (2022). Quizlet and podcasts: Effects on vocabulary acquisition. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 35(7), 1407-1436. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2020.1802601>
- Büyükaslan, A. (2007, May). Yabancı dil Türkçenin öğretilmesinde yeni yöntemler: Bilişim uygulamaları, çözüm önerileri [New methods in teaching Turkish as a foreign language: ICT applications, solution proposals]. *Proceedings of the I. International Computer and Instructional Technologies Education Symposium (ICITS)* (pp. 1–17). Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University.
- Büyüköztürk, Ş. (2007). *Deneysel desenler: Öntest-sontest kontrol grubu desen ve veri analizi*. Pegem A Yayıncılık.
- Büyüköztürk, Ş. (2010). *Sosyal bilimler için veri analizi el kitabı*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi Yayınları.
- Cilliers, E. J. (2017). The challenge of teaching Generation Z. *People: International Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(1), 188-198. <https://doi.org/10.20319/PIJSS.2017.31.188198>
- Çelik, S., & Toptaş, V. (2010). Vocabulary learning strategies of Turkish EFL learners. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 3(1), 62-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.07.013>
- Dahl, M. (2021). Vocabulary learning with Quizlet in higher education. *Journal of Teaching English for Specific and Academic Purposes*, 9(1), 17-29. <https://doi.org/10.22190/JTESAP2101017D>
- Deterding, S., Dixon, D., Khaled, R., & Nacke, L. (2011, September). From game design elements to gamefulness: Defining “gamification.” In *Proceedings of the 15th International Academic MindTrek Conference: Envisioning Future Media Environments* (pp. 9-15). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2181037.2181040>
- Dizon, G. (2016). Quizlet in the EFL classroom: Enhancing academic vocabulary acquisition of Japanese university students. *Teaching English with Technology*, 16(2), 40-56. <https://www.tewtjournal.org>
- Eryılmaz, R. (2025). İkinci dil olarak Türkçe öğretiminde dijital oyunlaştırma yaklaşımıyla kelime öğretimi. *Jass Studies - The Journal of Academic Social Science Studies*, 17(103), 91-108. <https://doi.org/10.29228/JASSS.80188>
- Eyibil, E., & Göçen, G. (2025). Yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğrenenlere sözcük öğretiminde Quizlet kullanımının etkisi. *Journal of History School*, 76, 2014-2053. <https://doi.org/10.29228/joh.78450>

- García-Ruiz, P., & Gómez-Domínguez, M. (2019). El uso de Quizlet para mejorar la adquisición de vocabulario de la L2. *Revista de Lingüística y Lenguas Aplicadas*, 14(1), 65-76. <https://doi.org/10.4995/rlyla.2019.11670>
- Groot, P. J. M. (2000). Computer assisted second language vocabulary acquisition. *Language Learning & Technology*, 4(1), 56-76.
- Hamari, J., Koivisto, J., & Sarsa, H. (2014, January). Does gamification work? A literature review of empirical studies on gamification. In *2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences* (pp. 3025-3034). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2014.377>
- İnal, E., & Arslanbaş, F. (2021). Türkçenin yabancı dil olarak uzaktan öğretiminde iletişim odaklı web 2.0 araçları ve uygulama örnekleri. *Bayburt Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 16(Özel Sayı), 228-249. <https://doi.org/10.35675/befdergi.850781>
- Kalyuga, M., Mantai, L., & Marrone, M. (2013). Efficient vocabulary learning through online activities. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 83, 35-38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.06.007>
- Kohnke, L. (2020). Exploring learner perception, experience and motivation of using a mobile app in L2 vocabulary acquisition. *International Journal of Computer-Assisted Language Learning and Teaching*, 10(1), 15-33. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJCALLT.2020010102>
- Kukulska-Hulme, A. (2009). *Will mobile learning change language learning?* *ReCALL*, 21(2), 157-165. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0958344009000202>
- Montaner-Villalba, S. (2019). The use of Quizlet to enhance vocabulary in the English language classroom. In F. Meunier, J. Van de Vyver, L. Bradley, & S. Thouésny (Eds.), *CALL and complexity - Short papers from EUROCALL 2019* (pp. 304-309). Research-publishing.net. <https://doi.org/10.14705/rpnet.2019.38.1027>
- Nguyen, T. H. H., & Nguyen, T. D. (2021). Using Quizlet in generating learners' autonomy in learning English vocabulary. *TNU Journal of Science and Technology*, 226(03), 34-42. <https://doi.org/10.34238/tnu-jst.4100>
- Okkan, A., & Aydın, S. (2020). The effects of the use of Quizlet on vocabulary learning motivation. *Language and Technology*, 2(1), 16-25. <https://izlik.org/JA42SR44XS>
- Pham, A. T. (2022). University students' perceptions on the use of Quizlet in learning vocabulary. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 17(7), 54-63. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v17i07.29073>
- Platzer, H. (2020). The role of Quizlet in vocabulary acquisition. *Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 17(2), 421-438. <http://e-flt.nus.edu.sg/>
- Quizlet. (n.d.). *About Quizlet*. Retrieved October 1, 2025, from <https://quizlet.com/mission>
- Sanosi, A. B. (2018). The effect of Quizlet on vocabulary acquisition. *Asian Journal of Education and e-Learning*, 6(4), 71-77. <https://doi.org/10.24203/ajeel.v6i4.5446>
- Sarıgül, K. (2021). Yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğretiminde çevrim içi süreç değerlendirme araçları. *Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey Üniversitesi Edebiyat Fakültesi Dergisi*, 4 (Yunus Emre ve Türkçe Yılı Yabancı Dil Olarak Türkçe Öğretimi Özel Sayısı), 56-80.

Siriwan, M. (2007). English vocabulary learning strategies employed by Rajabhat University students (Unpublished master's thesis). Suranaree University of Technology, Thailand.

Waluyo, B., & Bucol, J. L. (2021). The impact of gamified vocabulary learning using Quizlet on low-proficiency students. *Computer-Assisted Language Learning Electronic Journal*, 22(1), 158-179. <http://callej.org/journal/22-1/Waluyo-Bucol2021.pdf>

Yurtseven Yılmaz, H. (2023). Yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğretiminde mobil uygulamalar. In A. Okur & G. H. Demirdöven (Eds.), *Yabancı dil olarak dijital Türkçe öğretimi* (ss. 626-688). Sakarya Üniversitesi Yayınları.

Suggested Citation

Baştürk, Ş., İnan, K., Aksel, A., Keklik, H. & Tunç, A. (202X). Examining the Impact of Quizlet on Vocabulary Learning in Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language. *International Journal of Humanities and Art Research*, 11(2), 349-363. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20644890>

Author Contribution Statement

First Author: 40%

Second Author: 30%

Third Author: 20%

Other Author(s): 10%

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author(s) declares no conflict of interest.

Ethical Statement

All processes of this study, from planning to implementation, and from data collection to analysis, were conducted in accordance with the "Council of Higher Education Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive." None of the acts listed under the section "Violations of Research and Publication Ethics" were committed. Academic, ethical, and citation rules were followed, and no falsification of the data was carried out. This study has not been submitted to any other academic publication environment for evaluation.